

Does the Kaniadakis Distribution Represent Partial Equilibrium?

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In a previous note (1), we argued that if $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E/N$ are two a priori constraints in a system (linked with conserved quantities), then equilibrium occurs such that there is a conserved statistical quantity, a function of $p(e_i)$ s alone, invariant under $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ which contains the information of the two constraints. This implies that there must exist a function $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ where $F(p(e_i))$ only contains $p(e_i)$ terms (no e_i etc). This leads to the result: $\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = A \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) + B \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ which holds for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac, Bose-Einstein and even Tsallis case (for $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ replaced with $\sum_i p(e_i)^q$).

The problem is that the above scheme does not hold for the Kaniadakis situation if one uses: $F(p(e_i)) = 1/2k (p(e_i)^k - p(e_i)^{-k})$ and entropy density = $\int dp F(p)$. In particular, the Kaniadakis scheme bypasses the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ being contained in the entropy density and this suggests a lack of full equilibrium. Rather, there is strictly a focus on a statistical function $G(p)$ which is conserved and respects conservation of energy alone which is only part of the picture.

Quantitatively, one may see the issue present through: $\lim_{k \rightarrow 0} F(p) = \ln(p)$ and $\lim_{k \rightarrow 0}$ entropy density $\rightarrow p \ln(p)$, but $\lim_{k \rightarrow 0} d/dp$ entropy density $\neq -e_i/T dp(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ as in the MB case. In other words, $\lim_{k \rightarrow 0}$ and d/dp do not commute.

Thus, there is a disconnect between the Kaniadakis approach and the Maxwell-Boltzmann one even as k becomes tiny, suggesting that one does not really have a full equilibrium.

Entropy Density and Conserved Quantity Constraints

In (1), we argued that a system that is not in equilibrium contains N particles and a total energy E . Interactions occur and single particle energies change meaning $p(e_i)$ values change as well until one reaches an equilibrium state which is characterized by $p(e_i)$ being constant in time. In (1), we argued that one should have a conserved statistical quantity representing this equilibrium which is invariant under $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$. In other words, we argued that a statistical conserved quantity emerges for equilibrium which has conserved quantities embedded within. We note that as changes occur to $p(e_i)$ values, conservation of energy and particle number must be respected. Thus, in (1) we postulated a function:

$\sum_i G(p(e_i))$ (strictly of $p(e_i)$) ((1)) such that:

$$\sum_i dG(p(e_i)) = A \sum_i e_i dp(e_i) + B \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((2))$$

Conservation of energy and particle number should be present within the statistical conserved quantity $G(p(e_i))$. This appears to be the case for the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac, Bose-Einstein cases and even the Tsallis case, for $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = \text{number}$.

This implies that $dG(p(e_i))$ must yield two distinct terms as in ((2)), In the Fermi-Dirac case,

$$G(p(e_i)) = p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) + (1-p(e_i)) \ln(1-p(e_i)) \quad ((3)) \text{ and}$$

$$dG(p(e_i)) = dp(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)/(1-p(e_i))) + dp(e_i) - dp(e_i) \quad ((4))$$

One might argue that $dp(e_i)$ and $-dp(e_i)$ vanish, but they are present for each term in ((3)), in other words, particle conservation is present. Here: $\ln(p(e_i)/(1-p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$.

The problem with the above scenario is that it does not seem to apply to the Kaniadakis case.

Kaniadakis Situation

The Kaniadakis scenario is linked with:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \text{ where } F(p(e_i)) = 1/2k (p^k - p^{-k}) \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{For } k \rightarrow 0 \quad F(p(e_i)) \rightarrow \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((6))$$

The Kaniadakis entropy is sometimes given as: $\int dp F(p) = 1/2k (p^{k+1} / (k+1) - p^{k-1} / (k-1)) \quad ((7))$

In the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit one obtains $p \ln(p) \quad ((8))$

At first one might think that the Kaniadakis scenario evolves from the Maxwell-Boltzmann one, but we argue that this does not seem to be the case.

First, the constraints in the Kaniadakis case are: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = \text{eave} \quad ((9))$

These constraints apply to the Maxwell-Boltzmann scenario and so one would expect that a conserved statistical quantity $\sum_i G(p(e_i))$ which contains the two constraints would be associated with the MB distribution and not the Kaniadakis one. One may note, however, that the constraints ((9)) also apply to the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, which are not MB cases. The reason why one might focus on the MB distribution here, is that the Kaniadakis distribution has the following property:

$$p(e_i) p(-e_i) = 1 \quad ((10))$$

((10)) also holds for the MB case, suggesting a link between the two distributions. ((10)) does not hold for FD or BE cases, suggesting a distinct difference.

Here $p(e_i)$ Kaniadakis unnormalized = $(\sqrt{1+kx} + kx)^{1/k}$ where $x = -e_i/T \quad ((11))$

The Kaniadakis entropy ((7)) is created with consideration only being given to energy, not to $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. Conserved probability seems to be ignored altogether which is why we

suggest that the Kaniadakis distribution may only represent a partial equilibrium, one which is focused on energy.

To see mathematically why there seems to be an issue, one may note the following. Even though the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit of $F(p)$ and $\int dp F(p)$ yield the Maxwell-Boltzmann results,

$\lim_{k \rightarrow 0} \frac{d}{dp} \int dp F(p) \neq$ Maxwell-Boltzmann result ((12)) i.e.

$\lim_{k \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2k} \frac{d}{dp} (p^{k+1} / (1+k) - p^{1-k} / (1-k)) = \frac{1}{2k} dp (p^k - p^{-k}) = dp (-e^{i/T})$ ((13))

whereas the Maxwell-Boltzmann result is: $-e^{i/T} dp + dp$ ((14))

In other words, $\lim_{k \rightarrow 0}$ and d/dp in ((12)) do not commute.

Even for arbitrary small k values, the Kaniadakis result for ((12)) does not match the Maxwell-Boltzmann one. It is only for $k=0$ that one has a match. We suggest that the Kaniadakis distribution is not really a full equilibrium solution, but rather one linked to an energy conservation partial one.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in (1) we suggested that equilibrium occurs when one achieves a conserved statistical quantity, $\sum_i G(p(e_i))$ (strictly a function of $p(e_i)$) that is invariant under $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ which inherently contains the conserved quantities $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ and $\sum_i p(e_i)$. In the Tsallis case, $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ is replaced with $\sum_i p(e_i)^q$. This approach applies to the Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac, Bose-Einstein and Tsallis cases, but not to the Kaniadakis one. We suggest that even though the Kaniadakis case makes use of $F(p(e_i)) = -e^{i/T}$ such that $k \rightarrow 0$ $F(p(e_i)) = \ln(p)$ and entropy density $\int dp F(p)$ such that $\lim_{k \rightarrow 0}$ entropy density = $p \ln(p)$, nowhere is $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ enforced. To see this mathematically, one may note that:

$\lim_{k \rightarrow 0} \frac{d}{dp} \int dp F(p) \neq$ Maxwell-Boltzmann result..

This is identical to stating that $\lim_{k \rightarrow 0}$ and d/dp do not commute in the above expression. Thus, no matter how small k is, one does not have the above expression matching the MB case, suggesting that one does not have the same kind of full equilibrium represented by the Maxwell-Boltzmann situation. It seems rather that one has a partial equilibrium focused on energy conservation in the Kaniadakis case.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Role of Time Reversal and Possible Number of Reactions on Equilibrium Part 4 (preprint, zenodo, 2025)